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Home Automation System using IoT Google

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ABSTRACT

This research presents an innovative and awesome technology that everyone needed in this era, home automation with Google using Sinric Pro software. There are many other free automation software but why we selected Sinric Pro because of its easy and user-friendly interface. The ESP32 wroom32 microcontroller serves as the main controller or Brain of this system, allowing users to control and manage their living space from anywhere in the world with the help of the internet. Whenever new technology is introduced to the world, the world wants to see some factors in it. The first one is cost-effective, time-saving, problem-solving, easy to implement, and user-friendly. So, this home automation project includes all of these features. This is an ELV (Extra Low Voltage) system that the study designed, to turn it on to working mode it consumes about 2.2v to 5v. This system cannot only be implemented in newly designed houses or offices but is also easily implemented in any kind of building. With this circuit or system user can control all the desired appliances including the Refrigerator, deep freezer, Air conditioner, and almost all the appliances.

Keywords: IoT, Home automation, Google Home, Google Assistant.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today technology has this level that even people can do their daily routine work easily with the help of newly discovered technology, which took lots of time before, now just takes some seconds to be done using the power of the internet (Pu et al. 2023; Omolara et al., 2022). Nowadays energy crises are the major problem in the growth of any country so from time-to-time new technologies are introduced and because of this, these problems are going to end in some countries but not in the world (Halkos & Zisiadou 2023; Mara et al., 2022). So, on behalf of this, the study design and implement a system that can help the user control their living space from anywhere in the world using phones. This is a power-saving system. This system required a maximum of DC 5v for its activation and working mode which added this in the ELV (Extra Low Voltage) system. Nowadays, there are many home automation systems and also many companies offer them, but the thing that makes this project unique and more suitable is that there is no need to visit the field to implement this system as usually, the companies do (Stolojescu-Crisan et al., 2021; Tyagi et al., 2020). What all, the study should need from the user is how many and which device the user what to control or if they want to control. Also, the major difference between the company system and this local project is that it is very cost-effective and easy to implement at any kind of building, there is no need for any distraction (Bhadra et al., 2023; Oladimeji et al., 2023). In this system, the study also designed a mini circuit to control fan speed which is a pretty well approach instead of controlling it manually. Even to make it smarter there are two modes. In case of if there is an internet problem then it can be controlled manually as we all do in our daily routine. In the world of IoT (Internet of Things), day by day new technology is introduced to the world. In the field of IoT, this home automation project plays a vital role for researchers as well as investors (Umair et al., 2021; Ahmad & Zhang, 2021). The idea of this project came to my mind after the workshop on campus at HDL and ELV automation system, this was a 2-day workshop in which professionals talked about their comprehensive setup, how they installed it in the building and all the requirements and the major part of this is cost. So, keeping this in mind, the study designed a similar system that is even more friendly and even way too much cost-effective, and easy to implement and control.

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To make it more user-friendly, the study used Sinric Pro software. The interface of this software is easy to understand for everyone not only for designers. In this software users also select a time to control their devices and also, the user sets wattage power in the software so when the desired device consumes the given power it automatically turns off, is that not awesome! But the thing is this software is free for up to three devices for exceed we need to pay some amount as we exceed per device but this is way too cost-effective than companies offer. The software setup for this system is very easy. First, need to sign up for a Sinric Pro account using the user email address. After that create a room which is at the left side of the computer/laptop screen and then add room credentials as well as account credentials in C++ code which is then uploaded into ESP32 wroom32, the main controller of this system. After that user installs the Google Home app on his phone which links the Sinric Pro account with Google Home. That's all now users can use anything that they add and with which the user wants to connect the system. Figure 1 shows the software integration as ready reference.

Figure 1: Software Implementation

Source: Author's self extract.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study got the idea for this project from the workshop by HDL company help on campus. This 2-day workshop will encourage a lot to learn more about it and design it simple, effective, user-friendly, easy to implement, and the most demanding factor cost-effective. So, the study started designing it and successfully designed a very simple and more effective system. The results of this system were great and, thus, we implement it and use it in the field. Due to success in this project, the study gets the opportunity to work on a research project with professors.

The hardware integrates ESP32 wroom32 with electronic switches called relay and 5v power supply. The use of this is very simple, first need to install code in ESP32 wroom32 then connects Sinric Pro software with the Google Home app and that's all. The user interface of Google Home is as simple as other daily routine apps like WhatsApp and Face book but easier than that, user just needs to click on the specific device that they want to control (Turn it on or off) or the user also gives a voice command to turn on the device or off. The hardware setup is very easy, the main device or board which is used in this project is ESP32 wroom32, which controls all the functionality and working of hardware also called the brain of this system. The detailed flow chart of hardware integration is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Hardware Implementation

Source: Author's self extract.

3. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

3.1. Software Implementation

For designing the perfect system, first start from the software side, because it is important and all the hardware control depends upon software integration. First, create an account using the user email on Sinric Pro. Then use the app and the user's Wi-Fi credentials in C++ code which is then uploaded through Arduino IDE into ESP32 Wroom32. After that give the power to ESP32 and see if the LED lights up or not. And obviously, if we provide the correct detail in code then it lights up and shows connectivity to the internet. Here is a detailed Flow Chart for easy understanding,

3.2. Hardware Implementation Components used in the system

The following Hardware requirement is more than enough for designing the system, i.e.,

- ESP32 Wroom32
- 2.5v to 5v DC power supply
- Vero-Board (Dotted)
- Electronic Switch (Relay)
- Screw Connectors
- Wires
- Cover Box

The system may vary, as to how many devices or appliances the user wants to control or integrate with this system. The working principle of this device is based on the internet. When the internet is connected to the ESP32 then there is a blue LED that turns on indicating that Wi-Fi is connected to the system. Access the Google Home app to view the list of available room names displayed below. This indication confirms successful internet connectivity and flawless system operation, enabling users to exercise control over their preferences. The preceding text describes the hardware implementation system installed within the user's home (see, Figure 3).

Figure 3: System Architecture

Source: Author's sight

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After several tests and debugging the system, the overall results were impressive. The overall system performance is good and motivates to keep working on this system. The used system showcased it in the Exhibition and the audience's response after seeing the results was very impressive and motivated. The study implemented this system in the user's home and it works pretty well, the only challenge the study face is the network issue because in this area the network signal is weak which causes connectivity problems and the system is just messing up. But in cities, it's just working perfectly. For improved efficacy, the study assessed the functionality of the system through a relative residing in the United States. This individual remotely operates LED bulbs situated in a domicile located in Pakistan. A hyperlink to the video documenting this experimentation is provided below:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OVNvQF_bgoc

5. CONCLUSIONS

A significant contribution to this research project offers practical implications. This Home automation project has been practically implemented by using Google Home integrated with Sinric Pro, which is a user-friendly software for automation. The design of the system is according to the user's requirement by using the user's email address. The ESP32 Wroom32 is intelligent enough to manage all the control of the system. In summary, the ESP32 WROOM32 board exhibits a user-friendly interface and comprehensible functionality. Its ease of operation renders it a staple in numerous projects, chosen for its straightforward implementation. This board serves a pivotal function within the realm of IoT (Internet of Things).

As a foundational element within the dynamic domain of IoT, this technology serves as a catalyst for prospective exploration. Its application not only enhances ongoing research efforts but also cultivates a steadfast dedication to continuous engagement in future projects. Consequently, it contributes to the reinforcement of knowledge for upcoming opportunities.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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